

INDUCTIVE AND DEDUCTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING GRAMMAR FOR ESL LEARNERS

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ABSTRACT

Teaching is an interesting but in another site quite difficult process for every teacher, especially if it is ESL learners. For teaching properly, teacher should be not only skillful but also flexible, they should know each student's psychology and able to be in each student's place, to think like them, to learn like them. Knowing all learning styles gives more opportunity to teach a language in an effective way. This article gives information about the difference of four learning styles, how to conduct the lesson using them, their effectiveness for each student and their benefits for teachers. The main aim of this article contains to provide some tips of styles for teachers while teaching ESL learners. Furthermore, it gives some techniques how to combine all the styles (visual, auditory, kinesthetic, reading writing) into one lesson.

Keywords: benefits of learning styles, four types of learning style, techniques, visual, auditory, kinesthetic, reading writing,

Introduction

It is said that understanding children's learning way and preferences can benefit both students and teachers. It is impossible to teach only in one style into classroom among different type of learners. Because each student has personal learning way. For instance, someone can learn while watching movies or listening some audio or another one through books or magazines and we can not change their learning way. Achievements of students are mostly depend on their teacher's styles or the way they receive the instruction matches their learning style. Furthermore, it is suggested that teachers should take a balanced approach to teaching styles so that they can cope with various learning styles. There are 4 predominant learning styles such as visual, auditory, kinesthetic, reading writing.

Visual learning style.

This type of learners prefer learn by reading and seeing pictures. They remember and understand the subject through different signs or gestures. They are able to picture that they are learning in their head and can learn best by using different methods or techniques that are primarily visual. Now I want to include 8 foundational tips to help to the teachers for teaching better their visual learners

- Write down the vocabulary on the desk and ask them to copy it in their copybook.
 - Use the board efficiently. Try to explain the topic, write down necessary things on the board or let make the students the exercises on the board
 - use more charts or graphs
 - make your flashcards with movements and add more symbols
 - more games (flashcard games)
 - use videos, movies and of course slides
 - and the main encourage them to sit at the front
- and 3 strategies for the visual learners

Auditory learning style.

Listening and hearing, their way of learning. They would like listening to a subject over reading textbook or hearing instructions rather than figuring it out hands-on. There are some strategies I can mention for auditory learners into classroom. They give more opportunity to explain the subject in proper way .

1. reading the rules or words loud
2. making more listening tasks
3. making more discussions among students
4. watching different videos or movies (if you use the videos with subtitles, you can also help to visual learners)
5. using word association and mnemonics
6. making up songs or jingles

Kinesthetic learning style.

Kinesthetic learning style or second name tactile learning style includes learning by touching materials. This type of learners techniques are used in combination with visual or auditory study techniques, producing multisensory learning. There are some activities for teaching kinesthetic learners.

- using represent key vocabulary words
- presenting different puppet shows and making them

- making artwork to represent different stories or situations
Adding physical activities is also helpful for such kind of learners such as: walking bouncing and etc during the lesson.

Reading and writing learners

According to Kolbs' theory concrete experience or reflective observation abstract conceptualization and active experimentation form a four-stage process transformed into effective learning. Applying his learning theory has benefits for students. So, Who are reading and writing learners, they are this type of learners who prefer to read and rewrite in order to learn effectively. By reading texts and making notes they can remember and understand better.

Conclusion.

Understanding different learning styles is to effectively learn how an individuals learn new information and how they can present the information back. In this article we tried to explain each style learner and the ways for teaching them. Also we showed how the styles can conduct with each other. We examine different kind of techniques which include different interesting colorful and beneficial task and exercises. Accommodating each student's style can result in improved attitudes toward learning as well as increased self esteem and academic achievements.

References

1. Brown, H. D. (2000). Principles of Language Learning and Teaching (4th ed.). New York: Pearson Education Company.
2. Brinton, D. M., Celce- Murcia, M. & Snow, M. A. (2014). Teaching English as a second or foreign language.
3. DeKeyser, R. M. (2005). What Makes Second-Language Grammar Difficult? A Review of Issues. *Language Learning*, 55(1), 1-25.
4. Ellis, R. (2010). Does Explicit Grammar Instruction Work? *Ninjal Project Review*, 2, 3-22
5. Gollin, J. (1998). Deductive vs. inductive language learning. *ELT Journal*, 52, 8
6. Gullette, C. C. & Keating, C. & Viens, C. (1942). Teaching a Modern Language. New York: F. S. Crofts.